

CAPACITATE AND REACH: INCREASE TEACHERS' RESEARCH CAPABILITY THROUGH PROJECT MARE

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ABSTRACT

This research paper focused on the increase in research performance among the Langgas National High School faculty members using Project MARE (Motivate and Activate Research Enthusiast). This study utilized a One-group pretest-posttest method under a Pre-experimental research design. On pre-survey, teacher-respondents' responses generally fall into poor with a weighted mean of 2.05 to 2.4; and very poor has a weighted mean of 1.65 to 1.9. Teachers find it laborious to conduct and gain knowledge on research for they are having challenges with different workloads and ancillaries. Upon the conduct of an intervention, the weighted mean rises from 3.25 up to 3.9 with an interpretation of acceptable on questions 1 to 10. Teacher-respondents' level of motivation in conducting action research, showed that during the pre-survey, six questions had a weighted mean that ranged from 2 to 2.9; three questions had a weighted mean that ranged from 3 to 3.25, and one question had a weighted mean of 1.85. Undeniably, upon the conduct of an intervention teachers' motivation increased to 3.25 up to 4.14. Motivation plays a pivotal role in boosting teachers' interest in research.

Keywords: *PROJECT MARE, Action Research, Teachers' Research Competence*

INTRODUCTION

What impact does research really have on education in teaching and learning? This particular question plaque not only the students but on teachers as well. According to specialists, there are numerous reasons why research is vital in the field of education. Research helps students become more self-sufficient; as a result of research, students improve their ability to ferret out knowledge on a given topic with a deeper functional dive into the subject matter under investigation. More than usual, conducting research permits students to see the current talks about a given topic.

Moreover, research provides a way to growth and prosperity; research integrates the known with the unknown. Research becomes the way to growth and prosperity. Existing knowledge, gleaned from past research, serves as the foundation for acquiring new knowledge. New knowledge is created as a result of new research. Thus, in the absence of inquiry, the knowledge continuum is severed. It sows the seeds of scientific inquiry in future generations. Today's globalized and highly competitive world requires younger generations to think critically and creatively in order to respond to potential issues. As a result of research and education, the next generation is inspired and prepared to discover new knowledge that will benefit our community.

However, despite its positive effects upon classroom teaching and learning (Mahani, 2012; O'Connor, Greene & Anderson, 2006), a number of studies have reported some factors that prevent teachers from doing research. Crowded teaching timetables, heavy teaching workloads (Kutlay, 2013; Morales, 2016; Ulla, 2018), insufficient research training (Ellis & Loughland, 2016), lack of research skills (Vásquez, 2017), lack of financial support, and limited time to do research (Norasmah & Chia, 2016) often constitute the primary challenges and concerns faced by teachers and other educators aspiring to undertake research.

In the Philippines, doing research has become one of the important professional development programs for teachers that is emphasized by the Department of Education (DepEd) and the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) (Ulla, 2017). Teachers both from private and public educational institutions are encouraged to conduct action research in order to identify and address the teaching and learning issues and concerns in their classrooms and in the school. Thus, doing research has now become a part of every teacher's teaching evaluation and performance appraisal at the end of the school year (Ulla, 2016). DepEd has ordered its school heads and administrators across the country to adopt the "enclosed Basic Education Research Agenda" which promotes the conduct of research in schools by teachers (DepEd, 2016). The purpose is to discover schools' issues and solutions and form a part of teachers' professional development and skills enhancement.

Langgas National High School, as one of the public schools in Infanta, is struggling to uplift and develop research capability among the teachers. For the past 5 years, only two teachers were able to finish and submit complete action research. The School Planning Team (SPT) saw the magnitude of the issue and the urgency of the matter. As a result, the research team crafted the action plan that highlighted a series of LAC sessions that would give teachers the "know-how" in research, and Project MARE was conceptualized.

Project MARE deals with motivating teachers to conduct research. It is imparting knowledge in writing and crafting action research that would address challenges encountered on school premises and other factors that would affect students' performance in school. Project MARE started last November, 2022. It was the onset of the first LAC session in designing action research.

Research Questions

This research paper focused on the increase in research performance among the Langgas National High School faculty members using Project MARE (Motivate and Activate Research Enthusiast). Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of motivation and knowledge in research of teacher-respondents before and after the intervention?
2. Is there a significant difference in the level of motivation of the teachers in research before and after the implementation of Project MARE?
3. What is the implication of the findings in Schools' Governance in SBM as to research?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized a One-group pretest-posttest method under a Pre-experimental research design

A One-group pretest-posttest is a single case observed at two-time points, one before the treatment and one after the treatment. Changes in the outcome of interest are presumed to be the result of the intervention or treatment. No control or comparison group is employed.

Research Locale

Langgas National High School is one of the Barangay Schools in Infanta, Quezon. It is a public school located in Brgy. Langgas Infanta, Quezon. This medium-sized school has a full-time principal, sixteen (15) junior high teachers, five (5) senior high teachers, two administrative support staff, and 476 students. Alitas, Anibong, Langgas, Bacong, and Balobo are among the neighboring barangays served by its five service zones. The researcher chose this school for the simplicity of doing the research, so the researcher additionally works as a teacher.

Population and sampling

The respondents were the Junior and Senior High School teachers in Langgas National High School. It includes 15 respondents from Junior High School and five respondents from Senior High School. Complete enumeration was employed to achieve the objective of the study.

Research Instrument

The researcher's primary research tool was a self-created pre-survey and post-survey form. The content of the questionnaire was evaluated by an Infanta District school head and two master teachers. The instrument is broken into three sections, the first of which comprises the respondents' demographic profile, such as age, educational achievement, status, and so on which are optional. The second part deals with the respondents' knowledge in creating and developing action research. The motivational level of respondents before and after the session is then assessed using ten questions. Using a Likert scale, respondents placed a checkmark next to each matching item. To test the level of reliability of the research instrument, the researcher conducted a dry-run in Alitas Elementary School and utilized Cronbach's Alpha method to measure its internal consistency in responses.

Data Gathering Procedure

These are the data-gathering processes that were taken into account for systematic data collection and consolidation:

1. Designed a survey instrument that addresses the research objectives and variables.
2. The professional expertise of Infanta District School Head and Master Teachers were used to validate the survey instrument's content.
3. The survey questionnaire was tested through a dry run from twenty (20) public teachers in Alitas Elementary School.
4. The researcher collaborated with the school principal on the research aims and objectives, including the duration of program implementation as well as the covered period in data collecting and instrument use.
5. Sent a letter to the school administrator requesting official documentation on Project MARE's progress.
6. Surveys were conducted among respondents before and after the intervention.
7. The results were tabulated and analyzed.

Statistical Treatment

To validate the survey questionnaire, Cronbach's alpha was used. The formula for Cronbach's alpha is:

$$\alpha = \frac{k}{k-1} \left(1 - \frac{\sum V_i}{V_t} \right)$$

...where: k refers to the number of scale items
 $\sigma_{y_i}^2$ refers to the variance associated with item i
 σ_x^2 refers to the variance associated with the observed total scores

To answer research question number one, the mean scores from the pretest and posttest were compared to determine whether or not the intervention gained positive results. The formula for getting mean scores is:

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum X}{N}$$

Where:

\bar{X} = Mean
 $\sum X$ = sum of scores
 N = total number of respondents

To answer question number two, the post-test and pretest mean scores were compared and tested for the significant difference using paired t-test. The formula for getting paired t-test is:

$$t = \frac{\sum d}{\sqrt{\frac{n(\sum d^2) - (\sum d)^2}{n-1}}}$$

Where:

d = difference per paired value
 n = number of samples

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Cronbach's Alpha Result

The Cronbach's Alpha for questions that include knowledge and understanding of conducting and writing action research was 0.94, indicating EXCELLENT internal consistency in the responses while the questions that deal with the levels of motivation of teachers in conducting action research was 0.89, indicating GOOD internal consistency in the responses.

Pre-Survey and Post-Survey Weighted Mean Result

TABLE 1. Teachers' Knowledge and Understanding in Conducting and Writing Action Research

Pre-survey			Post-survey		
	WEIGHTED MEAN	INTERPRETATION		WEIGHTED MEAN	INTERPRETATION
1	2.2	Poor	1	3.25	Acceptable
2	2.2	Poor	2	3.55	Acceptable
3	2.1	Poor	3	3.3	Acceptable
4	2.4	Poor	4	3.9	Acceptable
5	1.95	Very Poor	5	3.6	Acceptable
6	2.05	Poor	6	3.47	Acceptable
7	1.7	Very Poor	7	3.45	Acceptable
8	1.65	Very Poor	8	3.35	Acceptable
9	2.35	Poor	9	3.9	Acceptable
10	1.85	Very Poor	10	3.35	Acceptable

5 – *Very Good*

4 – *Good*

3 – *Acceptable*

2 – *Poor*

1 – *Very Poor*

As viewed from Table 1, the weighted mean on teachers' knowledge and understanding in conducting and writing action research increased after the intervention was made.

On pre-survey, teacher-respondents' responses generally fall into poor with a weighted mean of 2.05 to 2.4; and very poor has a weighted mean of 1.65 to 1.9. Teachers find it laborious to conduct and gain knowledge on research for they are having challenges with different workloads and ancillaries. According to Cain, 2011, undertaking school or classroom-based research as a sort of professional development activity may be both gratifying and demanding for teachers and other education practitioners. Although undertaking research can enhance teachers' professional qualifications, skills, and experience, many instructors are hesitant to do so because it entails additional workloads on top of their teaching load, and a number of studies have looked into aspects related to this issue. This is in lined with the study of Borreo (2023), where the school research coordinators and enthusiasts experienced challenges in conducting an action research including the lack of training and having someone who will guide them in doing one. Hence, a research capacity building was proposed and implemented as to address these challenges.

TABLE 2. Level of Motivation of Teachers in Conducting Action Research

Pre-survey			Post-survey		
	Weighted Mean	Interpretation		Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1	2	Disagree	1	3.25	Neither Agree nor Disagree
2	2.4	Disagree	2	3.9	Neither Agree nor Disagree
3	2.65	Disagree	3	4	Agree
4	3.1	Neither Agree nor Disagree	4	4.1	Agree
5	3.25	Neither Agree nor Disagree	5	4.3	Agree
6	3	Neither Agree nor Disagree	6	4.2	Agree
7	2.9	Disagree	7	4.15	Agree
8	2.3	Disagree	8	4.05	Agree
9	2.4	Disagree	9	3.9	Neither Agree nor Disagree
10	1.85	Strongly Disagree	10	3.25	Neither Agree nor Disagree

- 5 – Strongly Agree
 4 – Agree
 3 – Neither Agree or Disagree
 2 – Disagree
 1 – Strongly Disagree

Table 2 reveals the weighted mean score of teacher-respondents on the level of motivation in conducting action research. It can be gleaned from the table that during the pre-survey, six questions had a weighted mean that ranged from 2 to 2.9; three questions had a weighted mean that ranged from 3 to 3.25, and one question had a weighted mean of 1.85.

Undeniably, upon the conduct of an intervention on teachers' motivation increased to 3.25 up to 4.14. Motivation plays a pivotal role in boosting teachers' interest in research. As Quain, 2019 stated that; when your employees are motivated by monetary and non-

monetary rewards, they are more inclined to feel empowered to perform at a consistently high level.

T-Test Result

Table 3. Significant difference in the level of motivation of the teachers in research before and after the implementation of Project MARE

Survey	Mean	SD	Difference between Means	T-Computed	P-value	Difference
Pre	23.15	8.93	13.88	-8.23	<0.001	Significant
Post	37.03	6.92				

Table 3 reveals the level of motivation of teacher-respondents in research before and after the intervention. The mean of the pre-survey and post-survey were 23.15 and 37.03 with a mean difference of 13.88; and a standard deviation of 8.93 and 6.92 respectively. The computed t-value at 0.05 levels of significance was -8.23 which showed that there was a significant difference between pre-survey and post-survey. Therefore, the null hypothesis “There is no significant difference in the level of motivation of the teachers in research before and after the implementation of Project MARE” is rejected. There was an improvement in the level of motivation in research according to teachers of Langgas National High School through Project MARE.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the action research the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Most of the respondents, before the intervention was conducted, had a poor to very poor knowledge of conducting research, however, upon injecting the intervention their knowledge and understanding of conducting research increased to an acceptable level.
2. The respondents’ motivation increased after the intervention of Project MARE.
3. There is a significant difference between pre-survey and post-survey of the intervention

Recommendations

The researcher submitted the following recommendations based on the conclusions:

1. LAC sessions should be utilized for further research-related understanding and capacity.
2. Enhancement of motivation to continuously entice and involve teachers in conducting action research.
3. The school research coordinator should keep herself abreast with the current

changes and developments in research to impart the “know-how” in crafting research to provide solutions to classroom-related issues

Compliance with Ethical Standards

For ethical and professional considerations, permission from the School Head was solicited, then, the participants were informed of the purpose of the study and assured that the results were held with the utmost confidentiality.

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